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Measurement Of Background Ionization Radiation Of Palm Oil Processing Clusters In Elele-Alimini, Emohua LGA, Rivers State In Nigeria

¹Chukwuemeka, S. O., ²Avwiri, G. O. & ³Chadumoren, Y. E.

¹Department of Physics
Department of Science Education,
Federal University, Lafia, Nigeria

^{2,3}Department of Physics
University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study aimed at determination of the levels of background ionizing radiation (BIR) exposure rate around various palm oil processing mills in Elele-Alimini, in Emohua LGA, Rivers state, Nigeria. Four palm oil processing clusters within the study area were selected, and a well calibrated Radalert 100 and a Geographical Positioning Device (GPS) were used. The results showed that, the mean BIR Exposure rate of the selected palm oil processing clusters used for this study were 0.010mR/h, 0.010mR/h, 0.009mR/h, and 0.009mR/h, which were below the recommended safe limit of 0.013mR/h, as stipulated by International Committee of Radiological Protection (ICPR). The mean value of the Excess Life Cancer Risk (ELCR) of the study area were 0.53×10^{-3} ; 0.47×10^{-3} ; 0.43×10^{-3} and 0.43×10^{-3} ; and they were above the ICPR standard value of 0.29×10^{-3} . The absorbed dose rates calculated were higher than the world weighted average of 59.00nGy/h, and the annual effective doses calculated were higher than the world average value of 0.07mSv/y. Based on these findings; the study area may have been radiologically contaminated, though contamination, has no immediate radiological health consequences for the population of the vicinity. Still, long-term health risks, such as cancer, are a possibility in the future due to accumulated doses.

Keywords: background ionizing radiation; effective dose; absorbed dose; excess lifetime cancer risk; palm oil processing Mills.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background ionization radiation is part of the natural environment and as such humans and other living organisms are continuously exposed. The main source of radiation includes cosmic rays that enter the earth from outer space and the naturally occurring radioactive elements of the uranium and thorium series and non – series radioactive potassium (Benson and Ugbede, 2018) which are characterized with half-lives comparable to the age of the earth and are present everywhere in the environment; in rocks, soil, water, sediments, foods and including the human body itself (UNSCEAR, 2008). The concentration and gamma radiation from the radioactive nuclides vary significantly, depending on the geological and geographical features of the region (Sharma et al., 2017). Radioactivity in our environment which consists of three important radionuclide series of uranium, thorium and actinium has been known to contribute

immensely to absorbed dose of an individual exposed to them (Oyebanjo *et al.*, 2012). The use of radiation sources in medical diagnosis and therapy, nuclear weapons, nuclear power plants, fertilizers production, research institutions as well as in consumers' products have contributed to increase in the background radiation exposure and doses. High radiation levels and doses in the environment are detrimental to human health, Ionizing radiations are highly energetic particles with characteristic high penetration power, when such radiation passes through the biological cell, it causes both excitation and ionization which alters the cell structure (Emelue *et al.*, 2014). Exposure to high levels of gamma radiation causes a number of harmful effects in man such as mutation and cancer of various types and different kinds of diseases (Taskin *et al.*, 2009). Owing to the recent drive of the Federal Government of Nigeria, to diversify the economy through agriculture, plantation of palm trees and processing of palm oil has been recognized as one of the alternative sources of income by many individuals especially in the rural areas such as Elele-Alimini village. The oil palm is a West African native plant that has grown in popularity, resulting in increased oil palm cultivation and commercial processing in Nigeria, raising major environmental issues owing to air emissions released during oil palm production.

Oil palm plantation has provided employment and economic sustenance for a vast number of countries, including Nigeria. Products from the oil palm plantation provide raw materials and feedstock for a number of dietary products for industry, (Loganathan *et al.*, 2017). Virgin palm oil contains various Vitamins that include Vitamin A, C and D (May and Nesaretnam, 2014). Palm oil production and processing is a key source of income for many people in Nigeria, particularly in the southern part of Nigeria. Human activities and practices can potentially affect the degree of radiation exposure in the environment (Karahan and Bayulken, 2000). Activities such as industrialization, application of fertilizers on farmlands, oil exploration, and mining activities have been reported to influence a higher degree of radionuclides in an environment (Ajayi and Dike, 2016). Thus, activities at the palm oil processing mills may influence the level of radiation in the area and, therefore, increase the indoor and outdoor radiation exposure levels, contributing significantly to irradiated doses through inhalation and direct contact.

The study on radiation levels in the different environment components helps assess the public dose rates due to radiation exposure (Ghazwa *et al.*, 2016). Despite various disputes over the stochastic effect of low radiation exposure, subsequent investigations have demonstrated that low radiation exposure, regardless of dose, can cause DNA damage (Usikalu *et al.*, 2016; Kawamura *et al.*, 2018; Ali *et al.*, 2020). Estimation of the radiation dose distribution is vital in assessing the health risk to a population and serves as a reference for documenting changes in environmental radioactivity due to anthropogenic activities (Obed *et al.*, 2005). As a result, the purpose of this study is to determine the level of background radiation exposure and its associated radiological hazard indices in and around selected palm oil processing mills in Elele-Alimini, Emohua local Government Area of River State, in Nigeria and ascertain the level of radiation exposure safety within the study area. The study will also contribute to the preservation of reference data to check probable changes in environmental radioactivity as a result of nuclear, industrial, and other human activities.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Location

The study areas are within the Eleme-Alimini, in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State, South-South Nigeria as shown in Figure 1. Elele-Alimini is about 45km away from Portharcourt which is the capital of Rivers state. Elele-Alimini has a land mass of about 0.619km² with a population of about 12,404 Four sites were selected for this study, namely; Oil mill roundabout palm oil processing cluster, Elele-Alimini; Behind Baptist Church palm oil processing cluster Elele-Alimini; Omadi palm oil processing cluster Elele-Alimini and Ahoada roadpalm oil processing cluster Elele-Alimini. Oil mill roundabout palm oil processing cluster is located along the east-west road at the Elele-Alimini roundabout with geographical coordinates of latitude N05°03.363' and longitude E006°43.550'. This cluster has about four different palm oil processing units, and produce about 1250 liters of palm oil daily. Behind Baptist Church palm oil processing cluster is located along East-West road, behind the Baptist church of Elele, it has four functional processing units, and produce about 1300 liters of palm oil daily, its geographical

coordinates are latitude N05°03.521' and longitude E006°43.550. Omadi palm oil processing cluster is located along Omadi – Ahoada road, Elele-Alimini. It has three functional processing units and produces about 1200 liters of palm oil daily, it has a geographical coordinates of latitude N05°03.509' and longitude E006°43.702'. Ahoada road palm oil processing cluster is located along Ahoada road, it has four palm oil processing clusters and produces about 1250 liters of palm oil daily, with a geographical coordinates of latitude N05°03.654' and a longitude of E006°43.598'.

Figure 1: Map of Elele-Alimini in Emohua Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria

2.2 Field Measurement:

An *in-situ* approach of background radiation measurement was preferred and adopted to enable samples maintain their original environmental characteristics, this was conducted using a well calibrated Radalet – 100 nuclear radiation monitoring meter (S.E. International Inc, Summer Town, USA) containing a Geiger-Muller tube capable of detecting alpha, beta, gamma and X-rays within the temperature range of – 10°C and 50°C was used to measure radiation levels. The Gieger muller tube generates a pulse current each time radiation passes through the tube and causes ionization (Avwiri *et al.*, 2012, Ononugbo *et al.*, 2016). Each pulse is electronically detected and registered as a count. The radiation meters were calibrated with a ¹³⁷Cs source of a specific energy and set to measure exposure rate in milli-Roetgen per hour. A geographical positioning system (GPS) was used to measure the precise position of sampling points. A number of fifteen (15) sampling points were considered for measurement at each of the selected oil mills in Elele-Alimini, with average taken and recorded at 5 minutes intervals at each point of the selected oil processing clusters. The readings were taken within the hours of 1300 and 1600 hours because exposure rate meter has a maximum response to environmental radiation within these hours (Louis *et al.*, 2005). The tube of the radiation meter was raised to a height of 1.0m above the earth surface with its window facing first the earth surface and then vertically downwards (Avwiri *et al.*, 2007, Ononugbo *et al.*, 2011).

Absorbed Dose Rate (ADR): The absorbed Dose Rate is calculated in nGy/h. Data obtained for the external exposure rate in μR/h was converted into absorbed dose rate nGy/h using the conversion factor given by Rafique *et al.*, (2014), to get equation 2.1a.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Absorbed dose rate} &= \text{Exposure dose rate} \times 8.7(\text{nGy/h}) && 2.1a \\ 1\mu\text{R/h} &= 8.7 \text{ nGy/h} && 2.1b \end{aligned}$$

The Annual Effective Dose Equivalent (AEDE): Measured absorbed gamma dose rates were used to calculate the annual effective dose equivalent (AEDE) received by individuals within and around the Elele-Alimini palm oil processing clusters. In calculating AEDE, dose conversion factor of 0.7 Sv/Gy and the occupancy factor for outdoor of 0.25 (6/24) was used. The annual effective was determined using equation 2.2 (UNSCEAR, 2000):

$$\text{ADED outdoor (mSv/y)} = \text{Dose rate(nGy/h)} \times 8760\text{h} \times 0.75\text{Sv/Gy} \times 0.25 \quad 2.2$$

Excess Life Cancer Risk (ELCR): The excess Lifetime Cancer Risk is used in radiation protection assessment to predict the probability of an individual developing cancer over his lifetime due to low radiation dose exposure, if it will occur at all.

$$\text{ELCR} = \text{AEDE} \times \text{DL} \times \text{RF} \quad 2.3a$$

Where DL is the average duration of life (70 years) and RF is the fatal cancer Risk Factor which uses a fatal cancer factor value of 0.05 for public exposure, (0.5 fatal cancer risk per sievert). For low dose background radiations which are considered to produce stochastic effects, ICRP 60 uses values of 0.05 for the public (Muhammad *et al.*, 2014).

$$\text{Therefore, ELCR} = \text{AEDE} \times 70 \times 0.05 \quad 2.3b$$

Equivalent Dose Rate: To estimate the whole-body equivalent dose rate over a period of 1 year, the National Council on Radiation Protection and Measurement (NCRPM) recommendation;

$$1\text{mR/h} = \frac{0.96 \times 24 \times 365}{100} \text{mSv/y} \quad 2.4$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

3.1 Results The results for the *in-situ* measurement of background ionizing radiation level and the calculated values for gamma dose, annual effective dose equivalent (AEDE) and excess lifetime cancer risk (ELCR) of the four selected palm oil processing clusters within the study area are presented in Tables 1-4 while Table 5 presents the summary of parameters calculated. Figures 3-7 show the comparison of the

calculated parameters with average (ICPR) world standard for the four palm oil processing clusters respectively.

Table 1. Mean Radiation Rate and the estimated radiation Risk parameters of Oil mill Roundabout palm oil processing cluster:

S/N	Sampling Point	GPR Readings	Exposure Dose Rate (mR/h)	Equivalent Dose (mSv/y)	Absorbed Dose (nGy/h)	AEDE outdoor (mSv/y)	ELCR x10 ⁻³
1	Sitting Area	N05°03.346' E006°43.575'	0.008	0.673	69.6	0.11	0.37
2	Pressing Point	N05°03.348' E006°43.575'	0.01	0.841	87.0	0.13	0.46
3	Bunch Point 1	N05°03.352' E006°43.572'	0.011	0.925	95.7	0.15	0.53
4	Bunch Point 2	N05°03.351' E006°43.568'	0.011	0.925	95.7	0.15	0.53
5	Transformer	N05°03.350' E006°43.573'	0.014	1.177	121.8	0.19	0.70
6	1Mm from Transformer	N05°03.348' E006°43.579'	0.014	1.177	121.8	0.19	0.70
7	2m from Transformer	N05°03.348' E006°43.583'	0.014	1.177	121.8	0.19	0.70
8	Karnel Point 1	N05°03.347' E006°43.584'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
9	Karnel Point 2	N05°03.346' E006°43.583	0.014	1.177	121.8	0.19	0.70
10	Boiling Point 1	N05°03.345' E006°43.581	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
11	Boiling Point 2	N05°03.344' E006°43.579'	0.008	0.673	69.6	0.11	0.37
12	Boiling Point 3	N05°03.342' E006°43.578'	0.011	0.925	95.7	0.15	0.53
13	Major Road	N05°03.346' E066°43.590'	0.010	0.841	87.0	0.13	0.46
14	Entrance Gate	N05°03.363' E066°43.592	0.011	0.925	95.7	0.15	0.53
15	1m from Gate	N05°03.357' E006°43.592'	0.012	1.009	104.4	0.16	0.56
	Mean		0.010±0.002	0.93±0.001	96.28±0.001	0.15±0.001	0.53±0.001

Table 2. Mean Radiation Rate and the estimated radiation Risk parameters of Behind Baptist Church palm oil processing cluster:

S/N	Sampling Point	GPR Readings	Exposure Dose Rate (mR/h)	Equivalent Dose (mSv/y)	Absorbed Dose (nGy/h)	AEDE outdoor (mSv/y)	ELCR x10 ⁻³
1	Chaff Point	N05°03.522' E006°43.547'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
2	Boiling Point 1	N05°03.523' E006°43.549'	0.010	0.841	87.0	0.13	0.46
3	1m from Boiling Point 1	N05°03.524' E006°43.551'	0.010	0.841	87.0	0.13	0.46
4	Boiling Point 2	N05°03.526' E006°43.548'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
5	1m from Boiling Point 2	N05°03.525' E006°43.545'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
6	Oil Storage Point	N05°03.524' E006°43.544'	0.008	0.673	69.6	0.11	0.37
7	Karnel Point 1	N05°03.522' E006°43.541'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
8	Karnel Selection Point	N05°03.519' E006°43.541'	0.014	1.177	121.8	0.19	0.70
9	Pressing Point	N05°03.519' E006°43.542	0.014	1.177	121.8	0.19	0.70
10	Karnel Point 2	N05°03.520' E006°43.546	0.011	0.925	95.7	0.15	0.53
11	1m From Gate	N05°03.522' E006°43.547'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
12	Entrance Gate	N05°03.521' E006°43.550'	0.008	0.673	69.6	0.11	0.37
13	Karnal Point 3	N05°03.517' E066°43.552'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
14	Newly Selected Karnal	N05°03.515' E066°43.550	0.010	0.841	87.0	0.13	0.46
15	Newly Selected Chaff	N05°03.519' E006°43.552'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
	Mean		0.010±0.002	0.83±0.001	85.84±0.002	0.13±0.002	0.47±0.002

Table 3. Mean Radiation Rate and the estimated radiation Risk parameters of Omadi palm oil processing cluster:

S/N	Sampling Point	GPR Readings	Exposure Dose Rate (mR/h)	Equivalent Dose (mSv/y)	Absorbed Dose (nGy/h)	AEDE outdoor (mSv/y)	ELCR x10 ⁻³
1	Pressing Point	N05°03.304' E006°43.695'	0.008	0.673	69.6	0.11	0.37
2	1m from Pressing Point	N05°03.505' E006°43.695'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
3	Oil Storage Point	N05°03.506' E006°43.694'	0.013	1.093	113.1	0.17	0.60
4	Chaff Point 1	N05°03.506' E006°43.593'	0.007	0.589	60.9	0.10	0.32
5	Selection Point	N05°03.506' E006°43.692'	0.008	0.673	69.6	0.11	0.37
6	1Mm from Selection Point	N05°03.506' E006°43.691'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
7	Chaff Point 2	N05°03.505' E006°43.692'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
8	Dried Chaff	N05°03.504' E006°43.692'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
9	Sliced Bunch	N05°03.503' E006°43.694	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
10	Un sliced Bunch	N05°03.502' E006°43.697'	0.011	0.925	95.7	0.15	0.53
11	Bunch Point	N05°03.505' E006°43.700'	0.010	0.841	87.0	0.13	0.46
12	Middle of the mill	N05°03.509' E006°43.702'	0.008	0.673	69.6	0.11	0.37
13	Boiling point	N05°03.512' E066°43.703'	0.010	0.841	87.0	0.13	0.46
14	Karnel Point 1	N05°03.514' E066°43.698	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
15	Karnel Point 2	N05°03.514' E006°43.698'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
	Mean		0.009±0.002	0.77±0.001	80.04±0.001	0.12±0.001	0.43±0.001

Table 4. Mean Radiation Rate and the estimated radiation Risk parameters of Ahoada Road palm oil processing cluster:

S/N	Sampling Point	GPR Readings	Exposure Dose Rate (mR/h)	Equivalent Dose (mSv/y)	Absorbed Dose (nGy/h)	AEDE outdoor (mSv/y)	ELCR x10 ⁻³
1	Boiling Point 1	N05°03.647' E006°43.600'	0.010	0.841	87.0	0.14	0.49
2	Boiling Point 2	N05°03.647' E006°43.599'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
3	Boiling Point 3	N05°03.640' E006°43.601'	0.008	0.673	69.6	0.11	0.37
4	Un sliced Bunch 1	N05°03.646' E006°43.604'	0.010	0.841	87.0	0.13	0.46
5	Un sliced Bunch 2	N05°03.647' E006°43.606'	0.010	0.841	87.0	0.13	0.46
6	Sliced Bunch 1	N05°03.645' E006°43.606'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
7	Sliced Bunch 2	N05°03.649' E006°43.607'	0.013	1.093	113.1	0.17	0.60
8	Dried Chaff	N05°03.665' E006°43.608'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
9	Pressing Machine	N05°03.645' E006°43.606	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
10	1m from Pressing Machine	N05°03.651' E006°43.604'	0.008	0.673	69.6	0.11	0.37
11	Oil Storage Point	N05°03.651' E006°43.605'	0.008	0.673	69.6	0.11	0.37
12	Karnel Point 1	N05°03.652' E006°43.600'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
13	Karnel Point 2	N05°03.652' E066°43.597'	0.008	0.673	69.6	0.11	0.37
14	Gate	N05°03.654' E066°43.598	0.010	0.841	87.0	0.13	0.46
15	Major Road	N05°03.657' E006°43.599'	0.009	0.757	78.3	0.12	0.42
	Mean		0.009±0.002	0.78±0.001	80.62±0.001	0.12±0.001	0.43±0.001

Table 5: Mean Values of the Selected Palm Oil Processing Clusters of the Study Area.

S/N	Oil Palm Locations	Location Code	Exposure Dose Rate (mR/h)	Absorbed Dose (nGy/h)	AEDE Outdoor (mSv/y)	ELCR x 10 ⁻³
1	Round About Oil Mill	RAOM	0.010±0.002	96.28±0.001	0.15±0.001	0.53±0.001
2	Oil Mill Behind Baptist Church	OMBC	0.010±0.002	85.84±0.002	0.13±0.002	0.47±0.002
3	Omadi Oil mill	OOM	0.009±0.002	80.04±0.001	0.12±0.001	0.43±0.001
4	Ahoda Road Oil mill	AROM	0.009±0.002	80.6±0.001	0.12±0.001	0.43±0.001

3.3 DISCUSSION

The background ionization radiation level and radiation health risk parameters of the four oil mill clusters in Elele-Alimini village in Emohua local Government Area of Rivers State as presented in Tables 1 to 4, have values of radiation exposure level that ranges from 0.008mR/h to 0.014 mR/h in the oil palm processing cluster of Elele roundabout, about 20% of the values obtained are higher than the ICRP standard of 0.013 mR/h for normal background ionizing radiation. The highest values were recorded in Transformer, 1m from transformer and 2m from transformer as shown in table 1. The values of radiation exposure level in the oil palm processing cluster, behind Baptist Church ranges from 0.008mR/h to 0.014mR/h, and about 13% of the values obtained are higher than the ICRP standard of 0.013mR/h for normal background ionization radiation, and the values of radiation exposure level in the oil palm processing cluster of Omadi ranges from 0.007mR/h to 0.013mR/h, and most of these values are lower with about 93.3%, than the ICRP standard value. The oil palm processing cluster of Ahoada Road value of radiation exposure level ranges from 0.008mR/h to 0.013mR/h, with about 93.3% of the values lower than the ICRP standard value. The oil palm processing clusters of Baptist church and Roundabout have higher values of radiation exposure, while those of Omadi and Ahoada have lower values, this variation may be due to the consistence of palm oil processing operation within the selected oil mills. The mean exposure dose rate of the selected oil mills within the study area are below the recommended safe limit of 0.013mR/h as stipulated by International Committee of Radiological Protection ICRP (2008). The results obtained were found to be lower than the result obtained Okitipupa by Omogunloye et al. (2022). The background ionization radiation variation within the study area might be due to natural background ionization radiation within the environment.

The absorbed dose varies from (69.6 to 121.8)nGy/h for Roundabout oil mill, (69.6 to 121.8)nGy/h for behind Baptist Church oil mill, (60.8 to 113.1)nGy/h for Omadi oil mill and (69.6 to 113.1)nGy/h for Ahoada oil mill; with mean values of 96.28nGy/h, 85.84nGy/h, 80.04nGy/h and 80.62nGy/h respectively. The mean absorbed dose of oil palm processing clusters of Omadi and Ahoada Road were below the standard value of 84.0nGy/h as stipulated by ICRP (2008), and also lower than the reported work at Enugu by Benson and Ugbede (2018). While the mean absorbed dose of oil palm processing clusters of Roundabout and Behind Baptist Church were relatively higher than the ICRP standard value of 80.0nGy/h.

The Annual Effective Dose Equivalent (AEDE) of the oil palm processing clusters of Roundabout, Baptist Church, Omadi and Ahoada, varies from (0.10 to 0.20) mSv/y with mean of 0.15mSv/y; (0.11 to 0.10) mSv/y with mean of 0.13mSv/y; (0.11 to 0.19) mSv/y with mean of 0.12mSv/y; and (0.11 to 0.19) mSv/y with mean of 0.12mSv/y, respectively. The AEDE of the study area are below the stipulated value of ICRP (2008) and is within the range of reported work at onne by Ononugbo et al. (2016).

The mean value of the Excess Life Cancer Risk (ELCR) of the study area were 0.53×10^{-3} ; 0.47×10^{-3} ; 0.43×10^{-3} and 0.43×10^{-3} for oil palm processing clusters of Roundabout, Baptist Church, Omadi and Ahoada respectively. The result of the Excess Life Cancer Risk obtained were higher than the standard value of 0.29×10^{-3} and lower than the reported work at Opkosi Ukwu and Uburu by Avwiri, et al (2016). The variation in the ELCR within the study area may be due to alteration of the concentration of radionuclides and also human activities within the area. The Excess Life Cancer Risk (ELCR) of the selected oil mills of the study area, relatively exceeded the worldwide average value of 0.29×10^{-3} , and lower than the work carried out by Agbalagba (2017), this implied that the residents of the area may develop cancer in future if continuously exposed to the high value of radiation within the area.

4. CONCLUSION

This study assessed the background radiation exposure around selected palm oil processing mills in Elele-Alimini village of Emohua Local Government Area of River State, using Radalert – 100 and Global Positioning System (GPS). Its associated radiological hazard indices such as the absorbed dose rate, annual effective dose equivalent and the excess lifetime cancer risk were calculated.

The following results were obtained from this study:

1. The highest exposure rate of 0.010mR/h was measured at oil mills of Round About and oil mills Behind Baptist church.
2. Minimum and maximum Absorbed dose rate value of 80.04 nGy/h and 96.28 nGy/h respectively were obtained from oil mill of Omadi and oil mill of Round About.
3. Mean values of outdoor gamma doses were found to be greater than the world population weighted average dose rates of 89.0 nGyh⁻¹ (UNSCEAR, 2008), in Round About oil mill with 96.28nGy/h while that of Omadi with 80.04nGy/h is less than the world average dose.
4. Estimated mean values of Annual Effective Dose Equivalent for outdoor exposure has a maximum of 0.15mSv/y and a minimum of 0.12mSv/y in Round About and Omadi oil mills respectively.
5. ELCR for outdoor exposure for has a maximum of 0.53×10^{-3} , in oil mill Round About and a minimum of 0.43×10^{-3} in Omadi oil mill.

Though our results showed high level of gamma dose rates, it may not have any immediate health hazards but could lead to some radiological problems for long term exposure of people living or working within the clusters.

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